

5G Technology and its Health Impact

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Abstract --Technology has become an integral part of modern society, revolutionizing various aspects of human life. However, its widespread use has raised concerns about its potential health impact. Title: 5G Technology and Its Health Impact. The advent of 5G technology has sparked both excitement and concerns regarding its potential impact on human health. 5G technology promises unprecedented speed, capacity, and connectivity, enabling a wide range of applications across various sectors. However, concerns have been raised regarding the potential health effects of prolonged exposure to the electromagnetic radiation emitted by 5G infrastructure. Extensive research has been conducted to evaluate the biological effects of radiofrequency electromagnetic fields (RF-EMF) emitted by 5G devices and base stations. While some studies have reported no significant health risks, others suggest possible links to adverse health outcomes, such as increased cancer risk, reproductive disorders, and neurological effects. Critics argue that the higher frequency and shorter wavelength of 5G radiation may lead to increased absorption and penetration into human tissues, potentially causing cellular damage. However, regulatory bodies and organizations such as the World Health Organization assert that current scientific evidence does not support a causal relationship between 5G technology and adverse health effects. To mitigate potential health risks, guidelines and safety standards are being developed to regulate and limit human exposure to RF-EMF. Further research is needed to better understand the long-term effects of 5G technology on human health, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation are essential to ensure the safe deployment of this revolutionary technology.

Keyword -- 5G, Radiation, Health, radio frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's technological landscape, the advancement and refinement of technology are imperative to provide additional features and capabilities that cater to current user requirements and fulfill productivity demands. Presently, most user applications prioritize high-speed broadband access over device technology. Over the years, mobile

communication technologies have strived to meet this demand, evident in the progression from first-generation to the current fifth-generation networks.

Unlike its predecessors, which focused on specific needs and ecosystems (such as mobile broadband), 5G stands out by being designed to support multiple services and tenants (Patrick Marsch, et al., 2018). The scope of 5G applications extends across various sectors such as transportation, healthcare, agriculture, and energy. This emerging technology enables the following key service types:

- **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB):** 5G enhances access to multimedia content, services, and data, providing improved performance and a more seamless user experience. With 5G speeds, gigabyte-sized multimedia content can be downloaded within seconds, surpassing the capabilities of previous technologies. Additionally, 5G improves radio coverage and capacity, delivering enhanced user data rates.
- **Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC):** 5G plays a pivotal role in the advent of Industry 4.0, revolutionizing various sectors of the economy. It provides reliable and low-latency wireless connectivity necessary for medical activities, autonomous driving, collaborative environments, and smart cities (Patrick Marsch, et al., 2018).
- **Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC):** The Internet of Things (IoT) aims to connect physical devices worldwide, necessitating a robust wireless network standard like 5G or higher. In IoT, "things" or objects can include individuals with implanted heart monitors, farm animals with biochip transponders, or automobiles equipped with sensors to monitor tire pressure. These objects are assigned Internet Protocol (IP) addresses and can transfer data over a network (Steve, 2020). Claims of 5G or IoT adversely affecting humans are currently unsubstantiated. When fully deployed, 5G will provide control over objects equipped with IP, making IoT adoption crucial for Africa and the rest of the world. Presently, industries and businesses in Africa are deploying sensors on a small scale, facilitating communication with remote servers. With the data rates offered by 5G, applications in sectors like agriculture and medicine would experience enhanced communication and interoperability (Patrick Marsch, et al., 2018).

Figure 1: Overview of 5G Connected Community
(Source: <http://www.emfexplained.info/?ID=25913>)

The agricultural and health sectors are expected to be the primary areas of application for most African countries. While previous generations of mobile technologies supporting data services have contributed to research efforts aimed at improving these sectors, the potential of 5G is even greater. However, concerns have arisen regarding the health implications of electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure to humans due to the high-frequency band utilized by 5G.

As 5G technology progresses towards global commercial deployment, including in Africa, there are still controversial design questions that require further research. In the current stage of 5G deployment, this paper not only provides an overview of the technology but also examines its potential health effects.

II. REVIEW OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES

In this section, a brief overview of the technological architectures ranging from the first Generation 1G system to 5G is carried out. Mobile telecommunication systems were first introduced in the early 1980s. 1G system dates back to early 1980s and were solely analogue systems. The spectral efficiency of such systems was very poor and thus had a very small capacity. The second generation (2G) systems deployed in the early 1990s provided a better spectral efficiency than 1G and were the first to use digital technology (Cox Christopher, 2012). These systems were originally designed to support only voice application but were later enhanced to support instant messaging through the Short Message Service (SMS). Popular amongst the 2G system was the Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM). This technology would later be upgraded to incorporate the General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) and Enhanced Data Rates for GSM Evolution (EDGE) to enable data download. By the year 2000, third generation (3G) systems were introduced and they proved to be a better replacement of previous systems. 3G systems could handle increased amount of data rates because they employed enhanced radio transmission and reception

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techniques that were different from their 2G predecessors. The world's dominant 3G system is the Universal Mobile Telecommunication System (UMTS). UMTS was developed from GSM by completely changing the technology used on the air interface, while keeping the core network almost unchanged. The system was later enhanced for data applications, by introducing the 3.5G technologies of high speed downlink packet access (HSDPA) and high speed uplink. The UMTS air interface has two slightly different implementations. Wideband code division multiple access (WCDMA) is the version that was originally specified, and the one that is currently used through most of the world. Time division synchronous code division multiple access (TD-SCDMA) is a derivative of WCDMA, which is also known as the low chip rate option of UMTS TDD mode. TD-SCDMA was developed in China, to minimize the country's dependence on Western technology and on royalty payments to Western companies. For many years, voice calls dominated the traffic in mobile telecommunication networks (Cox Christopher, 2012). The growth of mobile data proliferated with the advent of smart phones that could support the creation of applications by third party developers. This resulted to an explosion in the number and use of mobile applications. The Internet Service Providers (ISP) also contributed in the growth of mobile data usage with the introduction of flat rate charging schemes that permitted unlimited data downloads. At this point, data consumption soared, consequently making 2G and 3G networks to become congested in the years around 2010, leading to a requirement to increase network capacity (Cox Christopher, 2012). LTE was then introduced to increase capacity, by delivering peak data rates of 100 Mbps in the downlink and 50 Mbps in the uplink (though Initial systems could not meet this target). Research efforts were later geared towards enhancing the capabilities of LTE, and resulted to a specification known as LTE-Advanced which met and surpassed the initial specification for LTE. With the heightened demand for an enhanced mobile broadband experience, it was essential for the deployment of a technological framework that could handle such demands. The evolution of LTE plays an important part in the overall 5G radio-access solution. The International Telecommunication Union – Radio communication (ITU-R) defined a set of capabilities for 5G use case and usage scenarios, some of the key capabilities that are easily quantifiable are presented in figure 2. From the specifications, the maximum achievable data rate under ideal conditions is 20Gbit/s for downlink and 10Gbit/s for uplink. The spectral efficiency which gives the average data throughput per Hz of spectrum and per “cell,” for 5G was set to three times the spectrum efficiency target of 4G.

Figure 2: 5G key specifications (ErikDalman, et al, 2018)

Figure 3 presents a Mobile Standard Genealogy Evolution Model as developed by the author.

Figure 3.0: Mobile Standard Genealogy Evolution Model (Authors Model)

A. An Overview of 5G and the Electromagnetic Spectrum

The fundamental concept behind Wireless Communication and 5G technology revolves around Electromagnetic Field (EMF), also known as Electromagnetic Radiation (EMR) or Electromagnetic Energy (EME). EMF is transmitted from devices to systems and vice versa, spanning various infrastructure platforms. These fields are naturally present in our environment, originating from sources such as the earth, sun, and ionosphere (<http://www.emfexplained.info>). Unlike sound, electromagnetic radiation can travel through a vacuum and also through different media like air, fluids, and metals.

In wireless networking, the earth's surface, which is filled with air, serves as the medium for the propagation of wireless communication signals. The air-interface acts as the channel through which information flows between computer devices and the wireless infrastructure. It can be compared to a conversation between two individuals. As they move farther apart, it becomes more challenging to hear each other, particularly in the presence of loud noise. Similarly, wireless information signals travel through the air but possess unique properties that enable them to propagate over long distances. These signals are inaudible to humans, allowing for their amplification without causing disturbance to the human ear. However, the quality of transmission is influenced by obstacles in the air that can reduce or scatter the strength and range of the signals.

Figure 4.0: Electromagnetic Spectrum (Source: <http://www.emfexplained.info/?Page=25192>)

Electromagnetic fields exist everywhere in the environment including our home, school and work place. Electromagnetic fields are generated either by natural or human-made sources.

Natural sources of electric and magnetic fields encompass the Earth's Magnetic Field (responsible for compass orientation), lightning (generating EMF), and visible light (used for vision). On the other hand, human-made sources of electromagnetic fields include electrical appliances (such as vacuum cleaners, hair dryers, and refrigerators) and radio communication devices (like AM/FM radios, televisions, cordless phones, and mobile phones).

The Electromagnetic spectrum is divided into non-ionizing electromagnetic fields and ionizing electromagnetic fields. 5G technology, which falls under the non-ionizing electromagnetic field, utilizes radio frequency and microwave frequencies. Some electromagnetic waves possess immense energy capable of breaking chemical bonds between particles, known as ionizing radiation. Examples include X-rays, gamma-rays emitted by radioactive materials, and cosmic radiation. However, most artificial sources of electromagnetic fields, including radio signals, are classified as non-ionizing radiation. These fields do not have sufficient energy to break down chemical bonds within cells and tissues.

5G operates in licensed-spectrum bands ranging from below 1 GHz to approximately 60 GHz. Higher-frequency bands require careful regulation due to human exposure to RF electromagnetic fields. Regulations set limits on the maximum output power of user devices in higher-frequency bands to ensure human safety. International standards, such as those recommended by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) and specified by the

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Federal Communications Commission (FCC) in the US, establish safety margins to prevent excessive tissue heating caused by energy absorption (Erik Dalman, et al., 2018).

B. Electromagnetic fields (EMF) and Human Safety

Exposure to electromagnetic fields is not a new phenomenon for humans, as natural EMF has been present throughout history. However, with the advancement of technology and radio communications, human-made sources of electromagnetic fields have increased in recent times.

Extensive scientific research conducted over many decades has allowed national and international health authorities to establish safety limits for exposure to electromagnetic fields. These limits take into account various types of EMF and incorporate significant safety margins to ensure added protection. Radio waves, which fall under the non-ionizing electromagnetic spectrum, have been extensively studied for over 50 years. Numerous expert review groups have analyzed the research findings, and based on the body of evidence, there is no convincing evidence to suggest that exposure below the guidelines set by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) poses any health risks for adults or children.

The World Health Organization (WHO) states that extensive research has been conducted on possible health effects of exposure to different frequencies, including mobile phones and base stations. All reviews conducted thus far have indicated that exposures below the recommended limits set by ICNIRP do not produce any known adverse health effects. However, further research is needed to fill knowledge gaps and improve health risk assessments.

While the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified microwave radiations as possibly carcinogenic to humans in 2011, a systematic review on frequencies ranging from 6 to 100 GHz found insufficient information for a meaningful safety assessment.

There is a lack of specific studies on the health implications of 5G technology and non-ionizing radiation, resulting in conflicting findings in the available literature. However, some areas of potential concern include radiation-induced hypersensitivity reactions, interference with neuronal functions (such as cognitive ability), cancer induction, interference with fertility, cardiovascular abnormalities, and sleep disturbances. It is important to note that research outcomes can be influenced by human bias, which may lead to conflicting and confusing results if not rigorously controlled.

In conclusion, 5G technology has both advantages and disadvantages. Unbiased studies examining its health implications should be undertaken before its acceptance or rejection in Africa.

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